

Event Abstract

Distribution of ABO & Rh Blood Grouping Among Libyan Patients Admitted in Tripoli Medical Centre during 2015

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Background: The demand for blood and blood products has increased due to advances in medicine, population growth and increased life expectancy. ABO and Rh blood groups are most important blood groups in human beings. The frequency of four main blood group systems varies in population throughout the world and even in different parts of country. **Aim:** to identify distribution of ABO and Rh blood group system in Libyans.

Methods: A retrospective cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in largest tertiary referral governmental hospital (Tripoli Medical Centre) in Tripoli, Libya from beginning of January 2015 to end of December 2015. Data from blood bank records of ABO & Rh blood typing results for all admitted Libyan patients during the period of study were included except those of neonates. Data analysis was done by Chi-square test using SPSS software (version 16)

Results: study sample size was 8606. The highest percentage of blood groups in Libyan patients was related to blood group O (41.50%). The second most prevalent blood group was A (36.60 %) and AB blood group had the lowest percentage (5.10%) preceded by group B (16.80%). Majority (87.8%) of Libyan patients were Rh (D) positive and only (12.2%) were Rh negative. Blood group O + was the commonest type (36.2%) in our study while AB- is the least one (0.6 %), other blood groups were distributed in following order: A+ (32.2%) > B+ (14.8%) > O- (5.2%) > AB+ (4.5%) > A- (4.3%) > B- (2.0%).

Conclusion: we conclude that the distribution pattern of ABO and Rh blood groups among Libyans admitted

to TMC can be represented by the following formula:
O+ > A+ > B+ > O- > AB+ > A- > B- > AB.

Keywords: Libya, ABO & Rh blood grouping.

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